

Appendix to the SERENA Bundles cookbook I: Examples

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As a complementary brief document to support partners that use the cookbook, this appendix shows an exercise with the same data as shown in the bundles cookbook R script, but with some modifications to support the display and interpretation of the analysis.

Table 1 (modified from main bundles cookbook document)

Data type		Indicator	Unit	Resolution (km)	Year	Preprocessing
ST	SOC loss (eroded)	Eroded soil organic carbon	t C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	1	2000-2010	Data gaps filled through an iterative process using an IWD algorithm ^o
ST	Soil erosion	Soil loss by water	t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	0.1	2016	Data gaps filled through an iterative process using an IWD algorithm ^o
SES	Primary biomass production	Biomass production	Dimensionless (1-10)	1	2013	

Starting from the ESDAC data, a data gap-filling step was incorporated in to fill up the biomass and erosion raster layers since they had a high amount of gaps in relation to the C loss by erosion. This step was implemented by using a simple inverse distance weighting implemented in GRASS (GRASS Development Team, 2017).

The resulting filled raster layers can be shown in Fig. 1, where the gap filling of variables (e.g., raster layers) is summarised.

Fig. 1. Extent of data gap-filling implemented to reduce the number of cells with NULL values either (1) in both erosion and biomass on each cell (BF), (2) only biomass on each cell (BiF), (3) only erosion on each cell (ErF), or (4) cells where no gap-filling was performed (NF).

Using the gap-filled raster layers as data input, a bundle analysis as that shown in the cookbook and script documents was performed with $k=3$ clusters, but with different conditions to show the effect that different aspects of the analyses can have on the final result:

- 1) Non gap-filled data, min-max scaling, all EU area
- 2) Non gap-filled data, min-max scaling, only the Mediterranean South environmental zone (after Metzger et al. 2005)
- 3) Gap-filled data, min-max scaling, all EU area
- 4) Gap-filled data, no min-max scaling, all EU area

Table 2. Summary of main results of bundles' analyses ($k = 3$) varying some aspect of the analyses to see its effects on the final result. Values for the different SES/ST per bundle are cluster centroid values (e.g, bundles' means). For analysis condition id see main text. Er = erosion, Bio = biomass, SOC = eroded soil organic carbon. B1 = bundle 1, B2 = bundle 2, B3 = bundle 3. More detailed version of the bundles maps according to an analysis condition are shown below.

Condition settings									
Id	Gap filling	Scaling	Extent	Bundles' map	SES/ST	Er	Bio	SOC	Interpretation
1	N	Y	EU		B1	0.02	0.65	0.02	B2 is a high erosion, low biomass, high SOC eroded bundle, this is a low-quality one.
					B2	0.03	0.43	0.03	
					B3	0.02	0.81	0.02	
2	N	Y	Med		B1	0.04	0.22	0.03	Result is different when changing extension. B2 is still a relatively low quality bundle in terms of degradation, but with high biomass.
					B2	0.14	0.51	0.32	
					B3	0.03	0.56	0.04	
3	Y	Y	EU		B1	0.02	0.65	0.01	B3 is a high quality bundle, B2 is a low quality one, and b1 is intermediate. Filling gaps changes slightly the centroids values for the filled variables with respect to id 1. This is the application shown as example in the cookbook and R script
					B2	0.03	0.43	0.01	
					B3	0.01	0.81	0.01	
4	Y	N	EU		B1	10.3	6.1	0.11	The effect of using no-scaled variables is huge! The interpretation of high, medium and low quality bundles more or less remains, but the spatial distribution changes dramatically
					B2	28.6	5.7	0.19	
					B3	2.9	6.4	0.04	

Fig. 2. Spatial distribution of bundles for the analysis condition 1 (non gap-filled data, min-max scaling, all EU area).

Fig. 3. Spatial distribution of bundles for the analysis condition 2 (non gap-filled data, min-max scaling, only the Mediterranean South environmental zone).

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of bundles for the analysis condition 3 (gap-filled data, min-max scaling, all EU area).

Fig. 5. Spatial distribution of bundles for the analysis condition 4 (gap-filled data, no min-max scaling, all EU area).

References

GRASS Development Team. 2017. Geographic Resources Analysis Support System (GRASS) Software, Version 7.2. Open Source Geospatial Foundation. Electronic document: <https://grass.osgeo.org> , DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5176030

Metzger, M. J., Bunce, R. G. H., Jongman, R. H., Múcher, C. A., & Watkins, J. W. (2005). A climatic stratification of the environment of Europe. *Global ecology and biogeography*, 14(6), 549-563.